

Physicochemical Studies of some 3d-Bivalent Transition Metal Complexes of Glutathione (Reduced)

HARI PRASAD SRIVASTAVA* and RAJESH KUMAR SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 24 August 1993, accepted 13 January 1994

Manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes of glutathione (reduced) have been prepared. All these complexes are 1:1 binuclear and octahedral complexes in which the ligand glutathione acts as a hexadentate ligand coordinating with the central metal ions through oxygen, nitrogen and thiol group. In addition, all the complexes have been tested for their antifungal activity.

Metal-amino acid complexes have long been of interest as models for metal-ligand systems and complexes of bivalent metals such as Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} have been well characterised¹. In contrast, complexes of 3d-bivalent transition metals with glutathione, a tripeptide containing three amino acids as glutamic acid, cysteine and glycine are scarce and poorly characterised. This is presumably because in the ligand glutathione, there are eight potential sites through which binding to the metal may occur.

Fuhr and Rabenstein² determined binding of Cd, Zn, Pb and Hg by glutathione and found no detectable binding of Pb^{II} to group 2, but only to 5 and to 1 and 8 in some regions of pH. They found, 8 bound upto high pH where it is replaced by a hydroxo-group. Because of multiple potential sites of binding, glutathione provides a wide scope for the investigation on the behaviour of oxygen, sulphur and nitrogen ligands. In view of the biological importance of glutathione³, the present paper reports the synthesis of its metal complexes alongwith their physicochemical studies.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1.

Ir spectrum of glutathione showed a number of NHCO stretching vibrations⁴ in the range 3346–3256 cm^{-1} and NH_3^+ stretching and bending vibrations at 3128–3026 and 1537 cm^{-1} , whereas its metal complexes showed bands at 2960–2900, 2875–2800 and 1510–1515 cm^{-1} stretching and bending vibrations of NH_3^+ . NH_2 band was absent in the ligand while the

bands at 3416–3436 and 1618–1640 cm^{-1} corresponding to stretching and bending vibrations of the coordinated NH_2 group⁵ were observed in all the metal

TABLE I – ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour, m.p. °C)	Analysis % : Found/(Caled.)				
	C	H	N	S	M
$\text{Mn}_2(\text{GSH})_2$ (Brown, 360)	33.32 (33.34)	4.10 4.17	11.70 11.67	8.42 8.89	15.21 15.26
$\text{Co}_2(\text{GSH})_2$ (Brown, 360)	33.15 (32.97)	5.20 4.12	10.32 11.54	8.45 8.79	17.20 16.19
$\text{Ni}_2(\text{GSH})_2$ (Brown, 360)	32.85 (32.99)	4.02 4.12	11.35 11.55	8.56 8.79	16.05 16.14
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{GSH})_2$ (Blue, 235)	32.61 (32.56)	4.00 4.07	11.25 11.39	8.42 8.68	17.12 17.24
$\text{Zn}_2(\text{GSH})_2$ (White, 290)	32.21 (32.39)	4.15 4.05	11.22 11.34	8.35 8.64	17.42 17.65

complexes. The $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band of COOH group appearing at 1720 cm^{-1} in the ligand disappeared in its metal complexes on coordination while $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of amino acid appearing at 1601 cm^{-1} in the ligand shifted to higher frequency at 1648–1645 cm^{-1} in all the complexes. The band at 2525 cm^{-1} (SH) in glutathione disappeared on complexation, suggesting that thiol group is bonded with the metal ion. Stretching bands of M–N, M–O and M–S⁶ appeared at 420–440, 395–415 and 370–390 cm^{-1} respectively, in metal complexes which was absent in the ligand, supporting that the binding of glutathione with N, O and S occurred. Hence, it is observed that glutathione is bonded with the metal ion through oxygen and nitrogen (oxygen from the glutamyl

residue and another oxygen from glycol carboxyl group; nitrogen of amide group, the amino nitrogen and thiol group). A binuclear octahedral structure of the glutathione metal complexes is therefore proposed on the basis of magnetic susceptibility measurements and infrared spectral data. The solid state electronic spectra of all the complexes (Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II}) showed three absorption bands, except the Cu^{II} complex where only one band is observed.

The spectral bands at 465, 315 and 280 nm of the Mn^{II} complex correspond to transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$ (G), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$ (G) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (D) respectively. All these bands are due to *d-d* transitions. The Co^{II} complex exhibited three bands at 1212, 825 and 460 nm assigned to ${}^4T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}$ (F) \rightarrow ${}^4T_{1g}$ (P) transitions. All these bands are due to *d-d* transition. The Ni^{II} complex revealing bands at 905, 590 and 438 nm are assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) transitions. All these bands are due to *d-d* transition.

Electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex of glutathione showed a strong band at 640 nm, characteristic of octahedral stereochemistry⁷.

The room temperature magnetic moment values of the Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were found to be 5.8, 4.9 and 2.07 B.M. respectively, corresponding to their octahedral geometry⁸. The value for the Ni^{II} complex is somewhat higher (3.76 B.M.) than free octahedral (2.8–3.3 B.M.). The magnetic moment data show that all are normal and spin-free octahedral range.

Antifungal activity: Glutathione and its metal complexes were tested for their antifungal activity against some plant pathogenic fungi using slide germination technique. The results of antifungal activity of glutathione are presented in Table 2.

The germination % is low for the fungi *Helminthosporium Sp* and *Fusarium Sp* at 500 ppm concentration, which indicates that glutathione is more toxic and effective against the above fungi.

The results for the Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are presented in Tables 3 and 4 respectively. All other complexes were found ineffective against all the fungi tested.

Lower germination percentage value of the Co^{II} complex against *A. tenuissima*, indicates that it is more

toxic and effective against the fungus at 500 ppm concentration. Whereas higher value against *Fusarium Sp* indicates that it is less toxic and ineffective at the same concentration level. Further, the Co^{II} complex is more effective at 500 ppm concentration than at 250 ppm level. Lower germination percentage value of the Cu^{II}

TABLE 2 – EFFECT OF GLUTATHIONE ON SOME FUNGI

Fungus	Spore germination %		
	500 ppm	1000 ppm	Control water
<i>A. alternata</i>	88.0	92.5	92.5
<i>A. carthami</i>	88.5	91.0	92.0
<i>Fusarium Sp</i>	73.5	81.5	84.5
<i>Helminthosporium Sp.</i>	70.5	76.0	79.5
<i>A. tenuissima</i>	84.5	91.0	93.5

complex against *A. carthami*, indicates that it is more toxic and effective against the fungus at 1000 ppm concentration. Whereas the germination %age higher value against *Ustilago Sp*. shows it to be less toxic and ineffective against the fungus at 1000 ppm concentration. The Cu^{II} complex is more effective at 1000 ppm concentration than at 500 ppm level.

Experimental

Glutathione (reduced, Aldrich), sulphates of Mn^{II} and Cu^{II}, nitrates of Co^{II} and Zn^{II} and chloride of Ni^{II}, ethanol (all A.R. grade) were used as such.

Metal complexes: Glutathione complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were generally prepared by stirring equimolar (0.003 mol) aqueous ethanolic solutions (50 ml) of glutathione and the corresponding metal salts for 0.5 h. All the complexes were precipitated out at pH 5–6. The pH of the solution was increased by adding a few drops of alkali. The complexes were washed with water followed by few drops of ethanol.

TABLE 3 – EFFECT OF CO^{II} COMPLEX ON SOME FUNGI

Fungus	Spore germination %		
	500 ppm	250 ppm	Control 1% HCl
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	19.0	80.0	90.0
<i>A. tenuissima</i>	10.0	30.0	92.0
<i>A. sesamicola</i>	23.0	60.0	89.0
<i>Fusarium Sp</i>	32.5	80.0	92.0
<i>Helminthosporium turcicum</i>	16.5	72.0	95.0

and dried in vacuum desiccator.

Sulphur and metals were analysed using the standard literature procedures⁹. C, H, and N were analysed from Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

TABLE 4 – EFFECT OF Cu^{II} COMPLEX ON SOME FUNGI

Fungus	Spore germination %		
	1000 ppm	500 ppm	Control 1N HCl
<i>A. carthami</i>	10.0	22.0	75.0
<i>A. alternata</i>	14.5	26.5	89.0
<i>A. sesamicola</i>	20.0	45.0	90.0
<i>Fusarium</i> Sp.	15.0	32.0	85.0
<i>Ustilage</i> Sp.	25.0	40.0	82.0

Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Jasco FT-IR-5300 spectrophotometer and solid state electronic spectra (nujol) on a Varian Cary 2390 spectrophotometer. Room temperature magnetic measurement was done on a Cahn-Faraday magnetic balance using CoHg(SCN)₄ as the calibrant.

Acknowledgement

The authors record sincere thanks to Prof. P. K. Srivastava, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, for his constant encouragement and facilities. The authors are also grateful to Dr. U. P. Singh, Head of the Department of Mycology & Plant Pathology, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University for providing the result of antifungal activity of some compounds.

References

1. K. NAKAMOTO, Y. MORIMOTO and A. E. MARTELL, "Infrared Spectra of Metal Chelates of Amino Acids". 1961, p. 4528.
2. B. J. FUHR and D. L. RABENSTEIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 6944.
3. P. C. JOCELYN, "Biochemistry of the SII Group", Academic, London, 1972, p. 77; J. EISENBRAND and F. WEGEL, *Z. Physiol. Chem.*, 1941, **268**, 26; G. A. NEVILLE and T. DRAKENBERG, *Acta Chem. Scand., Ser. B*, 1974, **28**, 473; A. MORZOTTO, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 2193; D. J. DAIGLE and P. J. COTTY, *Can. J. Bot.*, 1991, **69**, 2353; S. L. BRAUER and K. E. WETTER-HAIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **113**, 3001; R. SHANTHI, K. S. NAGARAJA and M. R. UDUPA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 189; D. L. RABENSTEIN, "Coenzyme Factors", (Med. Aspects, Pt. A), 1989, p. 147; A. M. NOVI, *Science*, 1981, **212**, 541.
4. R. M. SILVERSTEIN, C. G. BASSLER and T. C. MORRILL, "Spectrophotometric Identification of Organic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1974, p. 108, 109.
5. L. BELLAMY, "Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1954, p.175
6. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of the Inorganic Coordination Compounds", 2nd ed., Wiley, New York, 1963, pp 167-283.
7. P. W. SELWOOD, "Magnetochemistry", Interscience, New York, 1956; T. M. DUNN in "Some Aspects of Crystal Field Theory", eds. T. M. DUNN, D. S. MC CLURE and R. G. PEARSON, New York, 1965; A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968; C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962.
8. L. L. ANTONI II, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **13**, 667; F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley-Eastern, New Delhi, 1967.
9. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Quantative Inorganic Analysis", Longman Green, London, 1978.

